

**THE IMPACT OF INCLUSIVE LEADERSHIP ON WORK ENGAGEMENT: THE
ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL DIVERSITY**

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Turkeyiauenstitu@aydin.edu.tr**ABSTRACT**

This study is important because it provides insights into the factors that contribute to work engagement and the role of inclusive leadership and psychological diversity in promoting employee engagement and welfare. In the first model of the Hierarchical Regression Analysis, it is seen that Inclusive Leadership could statistically explain work engagement. Since Inclusive Leadership can explain work engagement, it means the first hypothesis of the research is supported. But in the second, third and fourth models of the Hierarchical Regression Analysis, when psychological diversity interacts with inclusive leadership, it is found that the interaction cannot statistically explain work engagement. This means that the psychological diversity doesn't have an effect on the relationship of inclusive leadership and work engagement. The findings of this study can help organizations develop effective leadership strategies and manage diversity effectively, which can lead to improved organizational performance and employee satisfaction.

Keywords: Inclusive leadership, psychological diversity, work engagement, Afghanistan, Hierarchical regression

INTRODUCTION

Leadership has been widely and in-depth examined during the past few decades. It is challenging to emphasize how significant and crucial it is. Authorities and scholars, however, are unlikely to concur on the significant importance of leadership and the support that it requires (Johnson & Maclean, 2008). In a broader sense, leadership diversity involves many factors, including a mix of individuals, attitudes, traits, and input, besides the method that is designed to make the resulting combination function similarly. On the other hand, inclusive leadership is the capacity needed to handle the many viewpoints to achieve the intended goals in an efficient manner. Hollander (2008) has concluded that inclusive leadership is inevitably about the connections that can accomplish significant goals for mutual benefit between leaders and followers. Doing things with people rather than to them is required by the fundamental and vital inclusion of these leadership success levels. Additionally, one of its goals is to improve decision-making abilities and achieve desired outcomes without relying solely on one person's expertise. Thus he has suggested that inclusive leadership ensures an environment that minimizes partiality in input and output for all participants while promoting and appreciating cooperation and competitiveness as vital parts of the participatory process. In addition, it was noted that inclusive leadership has the power to influence political discourse, where its effects are particularly focused on gaining the consent of the government and taking their responsibility. Nembhard and Edmondson (2006) have defined inclusive leadership as leaders who express their willingness to accept and appreciate the responsibilities of others. They also define inclusive leadership as the argument or actions of the leader. The word "inclusive" connotes being a respected supplier and fully accountable for your commitment to achieving the finest results at any level. There is already a significant amount of research that illustrates how to handle challenging circumstances in an organization. Employees that are sufficiently engaged in their work value their relationships with coworkers and organizational leaders (Schneider & Macey, 2010). Accordingly, motivated individuals who are actively interested in their work have a positive, productive relationship with it (Kahn, 1990). Previous studies in this area have typically used one of two methods to analyze engagement experiences (Kahn, 1990). Psychological conditions for involvement are one strategy. whereas a person must have access to personal resources,

feel psychologically safe, and have a job that becomes sufficiently meaningful to be engaged in their career (May, et al, 2004). The job demand-resources model is another approach that bases participation on the accessibility of practical employment resources (Baker & Demerouti, 2014). Scholars who have reorganized the academic literature have found that academic research lags behind advancements in practice (Macey & Schneider, 2008). This is particularly clear in relation to the part inclusive leadership plays in boosting employee engagement.

Prior studies in this area have looked into a variety of influencing elements. However, it has been discovered that leadership and its many taxonomies have the most impact on employee engagement of all the variables (Loannidou, et al, 2016). In a similar vein, contemporary research has demonstrated a link between inclusive leadership and employee engagement in a variety of contexts. Similarly, earlier research indicates that psychological diversity is one of the key constructs that underlie the relationship between inclusive leadership and a variety of individual-level behaviors, including psychological diversity, employee job satisfaction, and organizational citizenship behavior (Choi, et al, 2015). However, there hasn't been a lot of research done in the past, particularly in developing countries like Afghanistan, on the impact of inclusive leadership on employee engagement. This study makes the case that inclusive leadership influences work engagement and that psychological diversity plays a role in mediating this effect. As a result, the current study might theoretically suggest that, in the context of Afghanistan as a war-torn country, inclusive leadership has a positive impact on work engagement through the mediation of psychological diversity. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, this study is a pioneering effort in the context of Afghanistan. The reason for choosing organizations in Afghanistan is due to a decline in worker engagement, which has an impact on the organization's expectations. Every organization has a goal for expansion and sustainability. Thus, in the modern world, organizations are represented by both their executives and their staff. Employers strive for engaged workers and invest a lot of money in improving work engagement. Organizations take the initiative through their leaders since workers are recruited to do specific tasks. Although there is no concrete evidence linking a leader's actions to followers' participation, the theory argues that psychological diversity is a key factor in this relationship. Each employee must be committed to and believe in the company's drivers, beliefs, and values to achieve this. This study investigates how inclusive leadership affects work engagement and calculates the influence of psychological diversity. It also looks at how psychological diversity might act as a mediator between inclusive leadership and work engagement. The article consists of five parts, the first part is the introduction, the second part is the literature review, the third part includes the theoretical framework, the fourth part is the analysis, and finally the conclusion.

LITERATURE REIVEW

A number of economists have examined the relationship between inclusive leadership and work engagement from various angles. The literature review regarding the relationship between inclusive leadership and work engagement are: Bing and his colleagues (2017) have conducted effects of inclusive leadership on employee voice behavior and team performance: The mediating of caring ethical environment with a descriptive methodology in China. The findings showed that inclusive leadership was positively correlated with employee voice behavior at the individual level and team performance at the team level and that a caring ethical environment mediated both the relationship between inclusive leadership and employee voice behavior at the individual level and the relationship between inclusive leadership and team performance at the team level. Rodreguiz (2018) has conducted research on inclusive leadership on work engagement: the moderating effect of psychological diversity environment the period focus is from 2004 to 2018. he decided to use a regression analysis using Andrew Hayes' PROCESS tool on SPSS was used. According to correlation results, inclusive leadership has a strong, favorable relationship with employee engagement. Hence, inclusive leaders can play a crucial role in reducing business and employee issues in organizations that may or may not have a congruent environment by working together and incorporating different styles of thinking. Yo (2018) has sought the impact of inclusive leadership on employee engagement by using a descriptive statistical analysis sampling research method. According to this empirical study, inclusive leadership is a good indicator of employee engagement. In other words, inclusive leadership increases employee engagement, and employees respond favorably to leaders who are more decisive in their actions. This study focused on

leadership; however, inclusive leadership placed a strong emphasis on two-way communication between leaders and employees. Huyen and others (2019) conducted the impact of inclusive leadership on job performance through the mediators in 2019 in China. using a structural equation model approach to analyze the survey data from respondents who worked for interior design and construction companies, inclusive leadership has a favorable impact on key determinants like employee well-being, person-job fit, and innovative behavior. Employee well-being and the person-work fit; however, had no appreciable direct influence on job performance. The study also found that inventive activity mediates the relationship between person-job fit and work success. A relationship between employee well-being and job performance may also be mediated by two other factors, including mutual regard and intrinsic motivation based on the research. Emmanuel (2020) has examined the impact of inclusive leadership on innovative work behavior period time of 2020 with a quantitative research methodology availability and measurement. According to this empirical study, inclusive leadership is a good indicator of employee engagement. In other words, inclusive leadership increases employee engagement, and employees respond favorably to more decisive leaders in their actions. This study focused on leadership; however, inclusive leadership placed a strong emphasis on two-way communication between leaders and employees. Priyadarshini & Rajappan (2020) have examined the effect of inclusive leadership on work engagement. using WarpPLS to examine the data. The results of the study show a strong correlation between inclusive leadership and work engagement. Also, the results show that inclusive leadership and work engagement have a moderating effect on person-job fit. According to the study, inclusive leadership behaviors by immediate superiors encourage and facilitate reciprocal work among their subordinates. Wahab and others (2021) have sought inclusive leadership and employee engagement through the mediating role of psychological empowerment in Afghanistan. Three hypotheses were created and validated using quantitative techniques and structural equation modeling with Smart PLS software to calculate the link between the variables indicated. According to the study's findings, inclusive leadership has a big impact on employee engagement. Results further indicate that the link between inclusive leadership and employee engagement is mediated by psychological empowerment. Aslan and others (2021) conducted research on the effect of inclusive leadership on work engagement in Turkey in 2021 using SPSS and AMOS software was applied. The findings showed that psychological safety partially mediates the relationship between inclusive leadership and work engagement and that inclusive leadership is a strong predictor of work engagement. According to the research, inclusive leadership has a favorable and significant impact on work engagement, which suggests that inclusive leadership raises work engagement. Bao (2021) sought inclusive leadership and work engagement through a moderated mediation model in 2021 by using hierarchical regression analysis and the processing technique created by Hayes's approach. The findings demonstrate that inclusive leadership, through person-job fit, is favorably associated with employee work engagement. The findings also show that the favorable direct association between inclusive leadership and person job fit as well as the indirect relationship between inclusive leadership and work engagement via person job fit are moderated by employees' sense of responsibility. Jin and his colleagues (2023) have used a survey design as a research method to assess the effect of inclusive leadership on innovative work behavior. The data was analyzed using SPSS and Mplus's structural equation modeling. The study demonstrated the relationship between inclusive leadership and creative workplace practices. The theory of inclusive leadership is effectively supplemented by research on inclusive leadership in the context of Chinese culture.

The literature review regarding the relationship between psychological diversity and work engagement are: Yee and his colleagues (2014) have examined the effect of a psychological environment for creativity on job satisfaction and work performance with a quantitative survey method in Malaysia. The purpose of this study was to look into how job performance and job satisfaction are affected by a creative psychological environment. The findings indicate that all variable associations were positively and significantly connected among electrical engineers who only worked in the Klang Valley: job satisfaction and work performance, a favorable psychological environment for creativity, the psychological environment for creativity, and work performance was found to be mediated by job satisfaction. Raina & Narayanan (2018) used a primary study approach to examine the impact of workforce diversity's primary dimension on employee engagement over the long period between 1997

and 2017. The impact of workforce diversity on results at the firm level has been examined in a wide range of studies. According to the review, gender and other factors were studied less frequently than the effects of age or generational disparities. Age, along with generational and temporal differences, had a substantial correlation with engagement, although gender and other factors had no meaningful influence. Jayavardana & Pryashantha (2019) studied the effect of workforce diversity on employee performance in Srilanka in the year 2019 and used a quantitative study technique. The findings showed that there was a positive and significant relationship between age diversity and employee performance. Increased age diversity was found to be positively correlated with employee performance, according to the findings of all these studies. The results of the analysis indicated that there was a significant and positive relationship between educational background diversity and employee performance. Lyndon and his colleagues (2020) are examined the employee reactiveness and inclusive leadership: time to manage diversity emotional in the time consuming 2020 with qualitative research methodology in India. The results demonstrated that supervisors had emotionally reactive and negative workers. The observation revealed that providing individualized feedback and coaching helped enhance efficacy. They felt energized by strategies like delegating. The investigation also revealed that freedom to experiment and empowerment both emerged as effective support mechanisms. Alshaabani and others (2021) have searched the impact of diversity management on employees' engagement: the role of organizational trust and job insecurity within the period time 2021 by quantitative research methodology. Findings show that diversity management positively and significantly affects employees' engagement, and this association is strongly and effectively moderated by organizational trust and job insecurity. As a result of reviewing the literature of the previous empirical studies, it can be concluded that they all found a positive and effective relationship between inclusive leadership and work engagement

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

THEORIES OF INCLUSIVE LEADERSHIP

The concept of inclusive leadership was first explored in Western education. Leader inclusivity is defined by Nembhard and Edmondson (2006) as a leader's verbal and behavioral performance to encourage and value staff input. According to Hollander (2012), inclusive leadership aims to create a partnership that is mutually advantageous for both leaders and their subordinates. The idea of inclusive leadership is an extension of Hollander's idea of leadership established by (Carmeli, et al, 2010). It is characterized as a leader's ability to demonstrate openness, accessibility, and connection with followers. In later research on inclusive leadership, this strategy has been frequently used (Choi, et al, 2016). According to this framework, inclusive leaders prove that they are independent thinkers. To create an environment where all employees are treated equally and there is no discrimination between members of the in-group and the out-group, inclusive leadership is necessary (Nishii, 2013). The inclusive leadership style is characterized by an emphasis on being people-oriented, ethical, and fair. It also demands equitable treatment concerning the attitudes of subordinates and is convinced of the importance of organizational coherence (Liu & Qi, 2017). Nembhard & Edmondson (2006) have advocated inclusive leadership in the field of management, which entails the speech and behavioral performance of leaders in motivating their subordinates to work and participate. They also supported the function of vicarious learning in building an inclusive environment. According to Hira and his partners (2012), inclusive leadership significantly improved the psychological stability of subordinates.

THEORIES OF WORK ENGAGEMENT

Kahan's (1992) work served as a source of inspiration for Rothbard (2001), who defined engagement as a two-dimensional motivational construct that includes attention (the cognitive availability and amount of time one spends thinking about a role) and absorption (the intensity of one's focus on a role). Some who view work engagement as the advantageous antithesis of burnout take a quite different tack (Maslach, et al, 2001). Maslach and his colleagues (1997) claim that the three burnout characteristics are the exact opposites of engagement, which is defined by energy, involvement, and efficacy. Job engagement is described and operationalized in its own right as a positive, rewarding state of mind that is marked by vigor, devotion, and absorption (Schaufeli, et al, 2002). The two main signs of burnout, tiredness, and cynicism, are seen as the exact opposites of vitality and dedication (Schaufeli & Taris, 2005). As we've seen, rather than the work position or job function, the organization serves as the standard in business contexts. Both academic conceptualizations that characterize engagement in

their own right contain elements that are behavioral-energetic (vigor), emotional (dedication), and cognitive (absorption).

THEORIES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL DIVERSITY

The main viewpoints on diversity can theoretically be divided into three categories. First, social injustice in organizations is the subject of the moral-ethical approach and the discrimination and fairness perspective (Ely & Thomas, 2001). The second approach is organizational and economic, which primarily focuses on how diversity affects results relating to the workplace (Milliken & Martins, 1996).

Third, the integration-and-learning perspective is founded by Ely & Thomas (2001) on the idea that different employees' talents, experiences, and insights may be useful resources for learning and change, are valued in the workgroup for achieving its objectives. The underlying deep-level diversity (such as attitudes, opinions, information, and values) that takes time for groups to emerge has since been distinguished by researchers from surface-level diversity (like demographic characteristics) that are more immediately apparent (Jackson, et al, 1995). Lastly, the virtue ethics approach of Milliken & Martins (1996) is more in line with deep-level diversity and emphasizes the role of emotions like forgiveness and favor in reducing bias, preventing rigid social categorization, and eliminating the conflicts of employing a diverse workforce as opposed to the business case for diversity. The value ethics approach also includes respecting connections and accepting each person's uniqueness, in addition to acknowledging the variety of emotions in the workplace (Wallace, et al, 2014). In addition to D&I policies, rules, and procedures, leaders must be able to communicate the importance of diversity internally for firms to become truly inclusive (Barak, 2015). With examples of openness, accessibility, and availability that strengthen the positive benefits of diversity on things like performance, engagement, work happiness, and perceived organizational support, this particular leadership style favorably affects how employees see inclusion (Blomme, et al, 2015). Employee engagement consequently increases as a result of these effects.

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

In this part, the findings of the study are given in two sections. The first section includes correlations, hierarchical regression analysis, and interaction tables. Lastly, demographic comparisons among the variables were made by difference tests in the third section.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

To examine the relationships between variables, a bivariate correlation analysis is done. In this analysis, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Method is conducted. The means, standard deviations, and correlations related to all factors are presented in Table 1. All correlations are significant at the 0.01 level and imply weak-to-mediator relationships, ranging from 0.018 to 0.426.

TABLE 1: MEANS, STANDARD DEVIATION AND CORRELATIONS FOR STUDY VARIABLES

	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3
1. Inclusive Leadership	4.34	0.14	1		
2. Work Engagement	4.16	0.17	0.426**	1	
3. Psychological Diversity	4.38	0.3	-0.062 (p=0.230)	-0.018 (p=0,728)	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

As seen in Table 1, a moderate positive relationship has been found between inclusive leadership and work engagement ($r = 0.426$, $p < 0.01$). But inclusive leadership and work engagement have no significant relationship with psychological diversity.

HIERARCHICAL REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Hierarchical regression analysis was done to establish statistically the mediator's impact. To see the variables in each model regardless of their degrees of significance, the regression in SPSS was performed in enter mode.

TABLE 2: RESULTS OF HIERARCHICAL REGRESSION ANALYSIS FOR WORK ENGAGEMENT

Dependent Variable: Work Engagement				
Variables	Beta	t	p	
Step 1				
Inclusive Leadership	0.426	9.162	0,000	
R= 0,426; R ² = 0,182; F= 83.935; p= 0,001				
Step 2				
Inclusive Leadership	0.427	9.144	0,000	
Psychological Diversity	0.008	0.180	0,857	
R= 0,427; R ² = 0,180; F= 41876; = 0,000				
Step 3				
Dependent Variable: Psychological Diversity				
Inclusive Leadership	0.062	1.444	0,230	
R= 0,062; R ² = 0,004; F= 1.444; p = 0,230				
Step 4				
Inclusive Leadership	0.427	9.144	0,000	
Psychological Diversity	0.010	0.180	0,857	

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Interaction -0,066 -1.162 0,246

R= 0,062; R²= 0,004; F= 736; p= 0,480

In the first model, it is seen that Inclusive Leadership could statistically explain work engagement (R²=0.182, p = 0.000 < 0.05). Since Inclusive Leadership can explain work engagement, it can be said that the first hypothesis of the research is supported.

But in the second, third and fourth models, when the mediator interacts with the independent variable, it is found that the interaction cannot statistically explain the dependent variable (R² = 0.004, p = 0.480 > 0.05). This means that the mediator does not have an effect on the relationship of independent and dependent variable.

DIFFERENCE TEST

Researchers can examine the differences between study variables based on demographic factors using SPSS's difference tests. Parametric and non-parametric tests are both a part of differential analysis. Non-parametric tests were utilized in this study since the sample sizes for the various groups were insufficient to perform a parametric test and the requirements for the variables' normality had not been met. Because the examined variables had two groups, the Mann-Whitney rank sum test was utilized as a non parametric analysis. Only significant findings are presented in this section.

ORGANIZATION

TABLE 3 THE DIFFERENCE OF INCLUSIVE LEADERSHIP ON CATEGORICAL ORGANIZATION

	Categorical organization	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Significance Level
Inclusive Leadership	Gov	23	4.35	100	0.516
	NGO	267	4.34	1158.78	
	Private	90	4.35	391.56	
	Total	380			

To determine the difference in the categorical organization of Inclusive Leadership, the Mann-Whitney rank sum test was applied. The findings indicate that there is no difference in inclusive leadership between the employees in all categories (μ Rank Govt= 4.35, μ Rank NGO=4.34, μ Rank Private =4.35) that is statistically significant (p= 0.516 > 0.05).

CONCLUSION

The study investigates the impact of inclusive leadership on work engagement with mediating role of psychological diversity. In the study the correlation analysis, Hierarchical Regression Analysis and difference test was used which correlation analysis determined stadard deviation, mean and median. Hierarchical regression analysis specify the interactions between variables. Diffrence test assesses the difference in the categorical organization of Inclusive Leadership between the employees in all

categories. The results of correlation analysis show a moderate positive relationship between inclusive leadership and work engagement. But inclusive leadership and work engagement have no significant relationship with psychological diversity. The result of hierarchical regression analysis in the first model of the Hierarchical Regression Analysis demonstrates that Inclusive Leadership could statistically explain work engagement. Since Inclusive Leadership can explain work engagement, it means the first hypothesis of the research is supported. But in the second, third and fourth models of the Hierarchical Regression Analysis, when psychological diversity interacts with inclusive leadership, it is found that the interaction cannot statistically explain work engagement. This means that the psychological diversity doesn't have an effect on the relationship of inclusive leadership and work engagement. The result of difference test show that there is no difference in inclusive leadership between the employees in all categories it means that it is statistically significant. Since inclusive leadership has a positive relationship on work engagement, then the Afghan business community can use it in a positive way, but on the other hand, psychological diversity has not established any kind of mediating relationship between the other two variables, so this research states that this variable has no influence on the performance of employees in organizations. According to the results obtained from this research that IV has a positive relationship on DV, so it is similar to the previous studies in the literature, but the mediating variable of this research is negative hence the previous studies in literature show a positive correlation. The reason that forced me to conduct a research under this title was the newness of the subject in Afghanistan, that not enough research has been done on this topic and it is still an opportunity for Afghan researchers to benefit from the results of this research. This study is important because it provides insights into the factors that contribute to work engagement and the role of inclusive leadership and psychological diversity in promoting employee engagement and welfare. The findings of this study can help organizations develop effective leadership strategies and manage diversity effectively, which can lead to improved organizational performance and employee satisfaction.

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